

DiSSCo Transition Project

**2nd Technical Workshop: DiSSCo Data
Management Plan and Standards for Taxon
Hypotheses**

Work Package 4 - Milestone 20

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Project DiSSCo Transition**Grant Agreement n°** 101130121**Start of the project** 01 December 2023**Duration** 18 months**Project Coordinator** Stichting Naturalis Biodiversity Center2nd Technical Workshop: DiSSCo Data**Milestone title** Management Plan and Standards for
Taxon Hypotheses**Milestone n°** 20**Means of verification** Report**Work Package** 4**Lead Beneficiary** NHM London**Due date of milestone** 28 February 2025**Actual submission date** 21-22 January 2025**Quality review** No**Milestone status**

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1.0	Achieved	21-22 January 2025	Kessy Abarenkov and Urmas Kõljalg, University of Tartu.	Workshop delivered.

Milestone report status

Version	Status	Date	Responsible	Actions
1.0	Draft 1.0	04/02/2025	Kessy Abarenkov	Sent to WP4 Leader and Coordinator for review.
1.0	Final 1.0	17/03/2025	Urmas Kõljalg	Finalised after resolving minor suggestions from reviewers. Submitted.

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Executive Summary

In the DiSSCo Transition project, Work Package 4 (WP4), titled “International Collaboration on (data) Standards” aims to facilitate ongoing development and adoption of new community standards. As part of our WP4 work, we prepared and delivered the second technical workshop on the machine-actionable DiSSCo Data Management Plan (DMP) and standards for taxon hypotheses. The preparation involved: creating a machine-actionable DMP (maDMP) for the DiSSCo infrastructure on PlutoF platform, incorporating example datasets and services to demonstrate its machine-actionability; developing an example implementation of the Taxon Concept Standard (TCS) applied to UNITE Taxon Hypotheses – a unified system for DNA-based fungal species linked to classification; designing workshop content, including presentations by the workshop authors and invited speakers, along with discussion points for participants.

We delivered the workshop to 40-50 participants in a hybrid workshop in Tartu, Estonia, on January 21-22, 2025.

All workshop materials, including PowerPoint slides, and Zoom recordings, were made available on the DiSSCo homepage¹.

Keywords

Data Management Plan (DMP), machine-actionable Data Management Plan (maDMP), Data Standards, User Workshop, Taxon Concept Schema (TCS), Taxon Hypotheses

¹ <https://www.dissco.eu/dissco-transition-dmp-standards-taxon-hypotheses>

1. Summary / Introduction

In the DiSSCo Transition project, Work Package 4 (WP4), titled “International Collaboration on (data) Standards” aims to facilitate ongoing development and adoption of new community standards. As part of our WP4 work, we prepared and delivered the second technical workshop on the machine-actionable DiSSCo Data Management Plan (DMP) and standards for taxon hypotheses. The workshop provided an overview of: (1) machine-actionability in DMPs, followed by a demonstration of machine-actionable DMP (maDMP) implementation on the PlutoF platform, and (2) the Taxon Concept Schema (TCS)² and the significant modifications introduced by the TCS 2 Task Group (Klazenga and Liljeblad, 2024). We explored how these updates enable the schema to accommodate and build practical applications on DNA-based taxon hypotheses (TH), especially those that lack formally described taxon names (Kõljalg et al., 2020). Additionally, Taxonomic Data Objects (Upham and Poelen 2024) – digital, machine-actionable taxonomic references – and their integration within an open, infrastructure-focused framework (Islam et al., 2024) were addressed in the context of this topic.

The preparation involved:

- Creating a machine-actionable DMP (maDMP) for the DiSSCo infrastructure on PlutoF platform, incorporating example datasets and services to demonstrate its machine-actionability.
- Developing an example implementation of the Taxon Concept Standard (TCS) applied to UNITE Taxon Hypotheses – a unified system for DNA-based fungal species linked to classification.
- Designing workshop content, including presentations by the workshop authors and invited speakers, along with discussion points for participants.

We delivered the workshop to 40-50 participants in a hybrid workshop in Tartu, Estonia, on January 21-22, 2025.

All workshop materials, including PowerPoint slides, and Zoom recordings, were made available on the DiSSCo homepage³.

2. Workshop Objectives

The workshop had the following five objectives for participants:

1. Provide an overview of machine-actionability in DMPs.
2. Present an overview of the DiSSCo Transition Project’s Task 3.3 activities and facilitate a review and discussion of the current DMP draft for the DiSSCo infrastructure.
3. Conduct a hands-on session to demonstrate the creation of maDMPs and provide an overview of the test implementation of DiSSCo’s maDMP on the PlutoF platform.

² <https://www.tdwg.org/standards/tcs>

³ <https://www.dissco.eu/dissco-transition-dmp-standards-taxon-hypotheses>

4. Introduce the Taxon Concept Standard (TCS) and its latest updates.
5. Explore how Taxon and Species Hypotheses can be managed as FAIR data.

3. Workshop Preparation

Content preparation consisted of two parts:

1. Technical
 - a. Developing a test machine-actionable DMP for the DiSSCo architecture on the PlutoF platform⁴. We identified datasets and services produced by the DiSSCo project to showcase the machine-actionable functionality of the DMP. This included searching and browsing project-related datasets in the DiSSCo Knowledgebase⁵ and Zenodo⁶.
 - b. Developing an example implementation of the TCS applied to UNITE Taxon Hypotheses⁷. During this process, we identified several issues with the current TCS standard that require further discussion and development.
2. Presentations (PowerPoint) – several presentations and hands-on session tutorial covering maDMPs and standards for taxon hypotheses.

4. Workshop Structure / Agenda

The workshop was divided into two parts, held on separate days. Day 1: “DiSSCo DMP for machine-actionability” (approximately 80 minutes) included the following sections:

- Introduction
- Overview of machine-actionability in Data Management Plans
- Overview of DiSSCo Transition Project’s Task 3.3 and Deliverable 3.3 activities
- Review and discussion of the current DMP draft for the DiSSCo Infrastructure
- Hands-on Session: Creating maDMPs in PlutoF
- Test implementation of DiSSCo’s maDMP on the PlutoF platform
- Discussion and feedback

Day 2: “Standards for Taxon Hypotheses” (approximately 135 minutes) included the following sections:

- Introduction
- Presentation by Niels Klazenga – “*The Taxon Concept Standard (TCS)*”
- Presentation by Urmas Kõljalg – “*UNITE standard of the Taxon Hypotheses*”
- Presentation by Sharif Islam – “*Taxon and Species Hypotheses as FAIR Data: BINs, OTUs, ASVs, TCS, and Beyond into the Biodiversity Data Ecosystem*”
- Coffee break
- Presentation by Tobias G. Frøslev – “*GBIF Backbone Taxonomy & Catalogue of Life*”
- Open discussion

⁴ <https://plutof.ut.ee>

⁵ <https://know.dissco.eu>

⁶ <https://zenodo.org>

⁷ https://github.com/kessya/TCS_UNITE_SH

5. Workshop Participants

The workshop had 67 registrants, primarily from Europe, with some participants from Australia and the United States. Some registrants attended only the first or second day. During the Zoom sessions, we observed approximately 35-40 participants on both days.

Registered participants were a mix of collections staff (e.g., curators/collection managers), technical staff (e.g., database and system developers), and DiSSCo National Nodes representatives.

6. Workshop Delivery

The workshop was delivered as a hybrid workshop run via Zoom at the University of Tartu, Estonia.

The workshop began with a presentation on the machine-actionability of DMPs, followed by a hands-on session and a demonstration of the DMP module on the PlutoF platform, led by Kessy Abarenkov. On the second day, invited speakers delivered a series of presentations on Taxon Concepts and Taxon Hypotheses Standards, followed by an open discussion led by Urmas Kõljalg.

7. Outcomes, Results, Challenges and Lessons Learned

We successfully delivered the workshop and received good verbal feedback; however, we did not collect structured survey feedback from participants.

Since the topic of Day 1 was new to many participants, the workshop primarily functioned as a presentation and demonstration of the test implementation rather than the planned hands-on and discussion session, resulting in shorter duration than expected.

Recommendation 1: For future training sessions, we recommend putting more effort into designing discussion points and preparing exercise sheets for participants to work through during the hands-on session.

The second day of the workshop, which featured four presentations, was followed by a very interesting and useful discussion that also involved participants who were not presenters. Based on this, we recommend inviting multiple presenters who can provide more depth on the topic covered in the workshop.

Recommendation 2: For future training sessions, we recommend inviting additional presenters to introduce the workshop topics in greater depth.

8. Future Work / Next Steps

We hope that the workshop will generate suggestions and feedback on the machine-actionable DMP for the DiSSCo infrastructure, including its draft document and deliverable (D3.3). We will continue working on implementing functionality and enhancing

the user interface for the machine-actionability of DMPs in PlutoF, as well as regularly updating the list of datasets and services that form part of the DiSSCo's maDMP to demonstrate its applicability and usefulness for managing data in research projects. Additionally, we will monitor the progress of the OStrails project⁸, which is developing the Plan-Track-Assess framework – a high-level, tool-independent framework that guides researchers, research managers, and funders in planning, tracking, and assessing the management of Digital Objects in their DMPs, in alignment with the FAIR principles – to stay informed about new developments and tools in this field.

We will continue developing and improving standards for Taxon Hypotheses by forwarding the knowledge and discussion outputs from the workshop to the Taxon Concept Schema 2 Task Group (Klazenga and Liljeblad, 2024). We will also continue building an implementation of the TCS using UNITE Taxon and Species Hypotheses as a test case.

9. Author/Contributor Contributions

Authors:

- Kessy Abarenkov – Technical preparation, workshop delivery, presentation
- Urmas Kõljalg – Workshop delivery, presentation

10. References

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⁸ <https://ostrails.eu>